

VARIANT ANATOMY OF THE AORTIC ARCH

Keywords— aortic arch, anatomy, variation, arteries, branching, angiology

I. INTRODUCTION

The high incidence of diseases of the human circulatory system necessitates frequent surgical interventions and diagnostic procedures [3]. In this regard, there is a need for a more in-depth study of the vascular system, including the variant anatomy of arteries, their topography, and branching patterns.

Vascular surgeries are characterized by specific features due to anatomical variability. Currently, surgical interventions for obliterating arterial diseases are widely performed worldwide. Numerous medical manuals on angiology exist; however, most emphasize the most common (classical) branching patterns.

II. AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study was to investigate variations in the branching of the aortic arch based on literature data and original anatomical research.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

We examined 11 human cadavers of both sexes aged 45–75 years using the following methods: anatomical dissection, morphometry, statistical analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study demonstrated significant variability in the branching patterns of the aortic arch.

A. M. Ochkurenko (1966) described a case where only two branches originated from the aortic arch: the brachiocephalic trunk and the left subclavian artery, while the left common carotid artery arose from the brachiocephalic trunk. This common carotid–brachiocephalic trunk was observed in 20% of cases (58 out of 300) [1].

One of the earliest large-scale studies (300 cadavers) by R. L. Herzenberg (1930) identified 36 variants of atypical branching. In 1.9% of cases, the right internal and external carotid arteries originated directly from the brachiocephalic trunk in the absence of the right common carotid artery. In 3.2% of cases, the right subclavian artery arose independently from the aortic arch and most commonly passed from left to right between the vertebral column and esophagus, less frequently between the trachea and esophagus, and rarely anterior to the trachea [1], [2].

Other authors (Dzhentaev Sh. D., Kondratyuk I. I., Yakimova E. B., 1960) described five branches arising from the aortic arch: right common carotid, left common carotid, left vertebral, left subclavian, and right subclavian arteries. The right subclavian artery originated from the descending aorta and passed from left to right between the esophagus and vertebral column [1], [2].

M. M. Pavlova (1965) reported that the thyroidea ima artery may also originate from the aortic arch, typically between the brachiocephalic trunk and the left common carotid artery [1].

In our own study, one out of 11 specimens (9%) demonstrated a non-classical branching pattern. The branches from right to left were arranged as follows: right common carotid artery, left common carotid artery, left subclavian artery, and right subclavian artery. The right subclavian artery originated posterior to the left one at a distance of 10 mm, then turned to the right and passed between the trachea and esophagus, bending the esophagus at a distance of 41 mm from its origin.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The study confirmed that the branches of the aortic arch exhibit significant variability.

Many anatomical variants have important clinical implications, as aberrant arterial trunks may alter the spatial relationships of vascular structures and organs of the anterior mediastinum, especially at the superior thoracic aperture.

Knowledge of aortic arch branching variations is essential due to the widespread use of angiographic diagnostic methods and surgical interventions for ischemic conditions caused by obstruction of aortic arch branches.

The study highlights the most common variations of aortic arch branching, which may be useful for surgeons in clinical practice.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. V. Kovanov and T. I. Anikina, *Surgical Anatomy of Human Arteries*. Moscow: Medicine, 1974, pp. 46–76.
- [2] D. Luzha, *X-ray Anatomy of the Vascular System*. Budapest: Hungarian Academy of Sciences Publishing House, 1974, pp. 36–41.
- [3] M. G. Prives, N. K. Lysenkov, and V. I. Bushkovich, *Human Anatomy*. St. Petersburg: SPbMAPO Publishing House, 2006, 720 p.

Authors:

1. Dzianis Dashkevich

Grodno State Medical University, Ulitsa Maksima Gor'kogo 80, 230009 Hrodna, Belarus
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2780-1930>

2. Dzmitry Valchkevich

Grodno State Medical University, Ulitsa Maksima Gor'kogo 80, 230009 Hrodna, Belarus
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3464-3158>

3. Agnieszka Anna Kiedik

Medical University of Gdansk, Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie 3a, 80-210 Gdańsk, Poland
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1507-8479>

Corresponding author:

Dzianis Dashkevich

Writing – rough preparation: Dzianis Dashkevich

Writing – review and editing: Agnieszka Anna Kiedik

Supervision: Dzmitry Valchkevich

Funding statement:

The study did not receive special funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement:

Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement:

Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement:

Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest Statement:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.